

INNOVATIVE INSTRUCTIONAL METHODS IN LEARNING LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *The given article is dedicated to learn language effectively. Using innovative methods in languages develop learners' attitude and motivate students. There are many innovative instructional methods as Thinkwane, different video games, Foster Connections Between Students, SWOT analysis, kahoot and others. Mentioned methods are not only beneficial but also productive for learning language.*

Keywords: *students, innovative, instructional methods, SWOT, Think wane, kahoot, foster connections, Renaissance university.*

XXI century gives to young people great opportunities to study and learn knowledge. Just as a modern world cannot be imagined without knowledge, it is impossible to imagine without educated youth. To get quality education, it is necessary to be able to choose a higher education institution that can provide high-quality and modern lessons. Especially, it is noted in learning languages. Learn languages are world's demand. As a student as well as learner, I maintain learning languages. I see myself in learning language and create new methods for learning them. When I started to study at Renaissance University, I noticed that English teachers taught us with different method and techniques. It really inspired me a lot and my interests in languages are increased. Using innovative instructional methods in the classroom can make learning easier and more effective. Experimenting with diverse strategies in the classroom is an iterative process that will assist teachers in promoting learning to encourage student growth. Education is a very powerful instrument for social change and transformation and innovative teaching practice is the only way to enhance the quality of our education. The purpose of education is not just making a student literate but adds rationale thinking, knowledge ability and self-sufficiency. When there is a willingness to change, there is hope for progress in any field. Creativity can be developed and innovation benefits both students and teachers.

The biggest challenge for any teacher is capturing each student's attention, and conveying ideas effectively enough to create a lasting impression. Using grammar only or doing exercises are not really effectively all the time. Because the same repetition every day can irritate students. If there are flamboyant ways of teaching students, observers will be inspired and there will be more indicators of scrutinizing language. Technology is also changing the classroom experience. Information and communication technology has made many innovations in the field of teaching and also made a drastic change from the old paradigm of teaching and learning. In the new paradigm of learning, the role of student is more important than teachers. The concepts of paperless and pen less classroom are emerging as an alternative to the old teaching learning method. Nowadays there is democratization of knowledge and the role of the teacher is changing to that of facilitator. We need to have interactive teaching and this changing role of education is inevitable with the introduction of innovative technological methods and producing a technologically-savvy generation of youths [4]. As a English learner, I focus on different methods. For instance, SWOT

analysis helps to four sides of the issue are identified as strong, weak, goal, and negative, and come to a certain conclusion. This innovative method shrink the time and give chances to think fast as well as write a report in a short time. There can be several topics and we can explain our ideas in four steps. It really gives to think as quick as possible; or via “Thinkwane” innovative method students can learn fast thinking [2]. Any topic in Thinkwane method can be optimal, because students use critical-thinking. There are some samples of my works:

Topic: *Students*

S- young generation who are creative and work hard. They have a strong passion to learn new.	W- students will not see significant internal changes until external issues are addressed and changed within the community.
O- students can achieve goals as non-stop youngsters. Government gives occasions to observers.	T- discipline is not always right way to study. There should be freedom to students to learn

Learning English is not really about vocabulary lists and grammar drills. It is about getting students to effectively communicate in English. It is important that creative teaching methods home in on this goal if we want to have a real impact to students.

Fostering connections between your students is one of the easiest and most useful ways to do this. You can help create a supportive classroom environment by making sure to carve time in lesson plans for group work and collaborative learning. Pair students work with different classmates, always giving them a common goal. As they pursue their goals and then achieve them, they’ll develop mutual understanding and encouragement and will support one another. This will create a safe place for students to put their English skills to use in a supportive environment that encourages creativity [5].

The following strategies are used to inspire creativity and success in the classroom. Change is necessary and through change, we are bound to fail or miss a beat. However, failing is ok. One of the most important lessons we teach our students is that they need to try and if they fail, then that’s ok. Failing is ok as long as we take lessons from that and try again. Though these strategies seem like we are taking a big leap into something new, we don’t have to apply them to our entire teaching strategy. Think of how you can use one or the other for a specific lesson. Maybe some subjects lend themselves to a project-based learning exercise while others benefit from simply asking open-ended questions.

I consider to try out different technologies like recording video lectures or using virtual classrooms when appropriate to venture into the digital experience. Maybe even have students create their own videos to learn and inform other students – our students are already creating videos with their friends, so maybe we can leverage their excitement and put it to good academic use.

As long as we're innovating, we are growing. Give it a go, it is always an exciting time to be in the classroom. It is especially exciting now while many are looking to introduce innovative teaching strategies as solutions to the challenge students face today. Rector of Renessans university, Barakayev Nusratilla Rajabovich provides us with these opportunities to study languages in high level.

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